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Charm physics at BESIII

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Abstract

BESIII has taken 2.93, 7.33 and 4.5 fb⁻¹ of e^+e^- collision data at energies of 3.773, 4.128-4.226 and 4.6-4.7 GeV, collecting the world largest dataset of $D\bar{D}$, $D_s\bar{D}_s^*$ and $\Lambda_c^+\bar{\Lambda}_c^-$ pairs. On the subject of charmed meson, we report the first experimental measurement of weak decay of charmed vector meson $D_s^{*+} \rightarrow e^+\nu_e$, the updated measurements of $|V_{cs}|$ in $D_s^+ \rightarrow \tau^+\nu_\tau$, $\tau^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu\bar{\nu}_\tau$ and the form factor study in $D_s^+ \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-e^+\nu_e$. In addition, we report the first amplitude analyses of $D_s^+ \rightarrow K_S^0K^+\pi^0$ including the observation of a new a_0 -like state with mass of 1.817 GeV/ c^2 and the improved measurement of the strong-phase difference in quantum-correlated $D^0\bar{D}^0$ decays. On the subject of charmed baryon, we report the form factor measurement in $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda e^+\nu_e$ and the observation of $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow pK^-e^+\nu_e$. Moreover, we report the first amplitude analysis of $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda\pi^+\pi^0$ and the studies of Cabibbo-suppressed $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma^0K^+$ and Σ^+K^0 decays. Finally, we present the prospect on measurements of charmed meson hadronic decays with the coming 20 fb⁻¹ of data being collected at 3.773 GeV by BESIII.

1 Introduction

The BESIII detector records symmetric e^+e^- collisions provided by the BEPCII storage ring, which operates with a peak luminosity of $1 \times 10^{33} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ in the center-of-mass energy range from 2.0 to 4.95 GeV [1]. Taking advantage of the advanced performance of the BESIII detector, large data samples of charmed hadron pairs are collected. The charmed meson pairs $D\bar{D}$ ($D_s\bar{D}_s^*$) are produced near the threshold energy of pair production 3.773 GeV (4.128-4.226 GeV) with integrated luminosity of 2.93 fb^{-1} (7.33 fb^{-1}), and the charmed baryon pairs $\Lambda_c^+\bar{\Lambda}_c^-$ are produced at energies 4.6-4.7 GeV with integrated luminosity of 4.5 fb^{-1} [2, 3, 4, 5]. Based on the world largest dataset of charm hadron pairs, charmed hadron decays can be studied with clean background without accompanying additional hadrons [6]. The double tag (DT) method is used for most of analyses, where the hadron pair is fully reconstructed. Only in Sec 4.3, the single tag (ST) method is used, where only one side of hadron pair is reconstructed. Throughout the paper, charge-conjugate modes are implicitly assumed, unless otherwise stated.

2 $D_{(s)}$ (semi-)leptonic decays

Charm meson (semi-)leptonic decays provide an ideal laboratory to test strong interaction and weak interaction mechanism. Measurements of these decays provide the accurate basis for deducing the decay constants, transition form factors (FFs) and Cabibbo-Kobayashi-Maskawa (CKM) matrix elements, which are helpful to calibrate the Lattice quantum chromodynamics (LQCD) calculations, test the unitarity of the CKM matrix and search for lepton flavor universality (LFU) violation in charm sector.

2.1 $D_s^{*+} \rightarrow e^+\nu_e$

As stated in Ref. [7], the $D_s^{*+} \rightarrow e^+\nu_e$ decay may be the most promising channel to observe the weak decay of a charmed vector meson. Recently, BESIII presents the first experimental study for this decay [8]. In the fit to the missing mass square (M_{miss}^2) spectrum, a hint for $D_s^{*+} \rightarrow e^+\nu_e$ is observed with a statistical significance of 2.9σ . The branching fraction (BF) of $D_s^{*+} \rightarrow e^+\nu_e$ is measured to be $(2.1_{-0.9}^{+1.2} \text{stat.} \pm 0.2_{\text{sys.}}) \times 10^{-5}$, corresponding to an upper limit of 4.0×10^{-5} at the 90% confidence level (CL). Taking the total width of the D_s^{*+} ($\Gamma_{D_s^{*+}}^{\text{total}} = (70 \pm 28) \text{ eV}$) predicted by LQCD and SM global fit result ($|V_{cs}| = 0.97349 \pm 0.00016$) as input, the decay constant of the D_s^{*+} is determined to be $f_{D_s^{*+}} = (213.6_{-45.8}^{+61.0} \text{stat.} \pm 43.9_{\text{sys.}}) \text{ MeV}$, corresponding to an upper limit of 353.8 MeV at the 90% CL. Combining with the world average values of $\mathcal{B}(D_s^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu)$ and $\frac{f_{D_s^{*+}}}{f_{D_s^+}} = 1.12 \pm 0.01$ averaged from LQCD calculation, this work also gives $\Gamma_{D_s^{*+}}^{\text{total}} = (121.9_{-52.2}^{+69.6} \pm 11.8) \text{ eV}$ which agrees with LQCD calculation within $\pm 1\sigma$. This result indirectly constrains the upper limit on the total width from MeV to keV level.

2.2 $D_s^+ \rightarrow \tau^+\nu_\tau, \tau^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu\bar{\nu}_\tau$

Since the massless neutrinos are undetected, the variable of $E_{\text{extra}}^{\text{tot}}$ has been adopted to analyze extra the signal $D_s^+ \rightarrow \tau^+\nu_\tau, \tau^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu\bar{\nu}_\tau$ [9], where $E_{\text{extra}}^{\text{tot}}$ denotes the total energy of the good isolated EMC showers which have not been used in ST selection. The signal yields are determined in the region $E_{\text{extra}}^{\text{tot}} < 0.4 \text{ GeV}$ by statistically subtracting the backgrounds extrapolated from the fits to $E_{\text{extra}}^{\text{tot}}$ in $E_{\text{extra}}^{\text{tot}} > 0.6 \text{ GeV}$. The BF of $D_s^+ \rightarrow \tau^+\nu_\tau$ is determined to be $(5.34 \pm 0.16_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.10_{\text{sys.}})\%$. Combining recent BESIII measurements using the decays $\tau^+ \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^0\bar{\nu}_\tau, \tau^+ \rightarrow e^+\nu_e\bar{\nu}_\tau, \tau^+ \rightarrow \mu^+\nu_\mu\bar{\nu}_\tau$ and $\tau^+ \rightarrow \pi^+\bar{\nu}_\tau$, and taking systematic uncertainties to be correlated among them, the average BF is determined to be $\mathcal{B}(D_s^+ \rightarrow \tau^+\nu_\tau) = (5.32 \pm 0.07_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.07_{\text{sys.}})\%$. From this result, it follows $f_{D_s^+} = (252.1 \pm 1.7_{\text{stat.}} \pm 2.0_{\text{sys.}}) \text{ MeV}$, $|V_{cs}| = 0.982 \pm$

$0.007_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.008_{\text{syst.}}$, and $R_{\tau/\mu} = 9.79 \pm 0.33$ which is consistent with the expectation based on the assumption of LFU.

2.3 $D_s^+ \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-e^+\nu_e$

Recently, BESIII has presented an analysis of the decay $D_s^+ \rightarrow f_0(980)e^+\nu_e$ with $f_0(980) \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ [10]. We observe the $f_0(980)$ in the $\pi^+\pi^-$ system and the BF of the decay $D_s^+ \rightarrow f_0(980)e^+\nu_e$ with $f_0(980) \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ is measured to be $(1.72 \pm 0.13_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.10_{\text{syst.}}) \times 10^{-3}$, which is 2.6 times more accurate than the previous measurement [11]. This measurement is important to probe the nature of $f_0(980)$. Using the relation between the BF and the mixing angle ϕ involved in the $q\bar{q}$ mixture picture for $f_0(980)$ as $\sin\phi\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(u\bar{u} + d\bar{d}) + \cos\phi(s\bar{s})$, the $s\bar{s}$ component is found to be dominant. A fit to the differential decay rate of the channel $D_s^+ \rightarrow f_0(980)e^+\nu_e$ is performed, and $f_+^{f_0}(0)|V_{cs}|$ is determined to be $0.504 \pm 0.017_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.035_{\text{syst.}}$ for the first time. Using $|V_{cs}|$ from SM global fit, $f_+^{f_0}(0)$ is determined to be $0.518 \pm 0.018_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.036_{\text{syst.}}$. Most theoretically predicted FFs and BFs depend on the angle ϕ with large uncertainty. Therefore, this measurement is important to constrain angle ϕ and probe the quark component in $f_0(980)$.

3 $D_{(s)}$ hadronic decays

The ground states of charmed meson $D_{(s)}$ can only decay weakly, so it provides an important test for the weak interaction mechanism. Furthermore, the strong interaction is always involved in the $D_{(s)}$ decay and the hadronization into final-state hadron. The precise measurement of decay BF can help to probe non-perturbative QCD, test various phenomenological model prediction and understand the $SU(3)$ flavor symmetry and its breaking effect. Amplitude analysis of multi-body hadronic charm meson decay is a powerful tool to investigate the possible intermediate state, enrich our understanding of light hadron spectroscopy, and test the different decay mechanisms, like W -exchange, W -annihilation, final-state interaction etc. Quantum-correlated (QC) $D^0\bar{D}^0$ dataset is one of the characteristic of BESIII [12]. The interference term of the decay amplitude of a DT event is sensitive to the strong-phase difference. The strong-phase measurement provides an important input for improving the precision in γ/ϕ_3 measurement which plays an important role in testing the SM describing the CP violation and probing for the possible new physics.

3.1 $D_s^+ \rightarrow K_S^0 K^+ \pi^0$

The first amplitude analysis of $D_s^+ \rightarrow K_S^0 K^+ \pi^0$ decay has been performed by BESIII [13]. The analysis was done with 1050 DT events with a signal purity of 94.7%, and the projections of the fit result are shown at Figure 1. In this analysis, the BF of $D_s^+ \rightarrow K_S^0 K^+ \pi^0$ is measured to be $(1.46 \pm 0.06_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.05_{\text{syst.}})\%$ and an a_0 -like state called $a_0(1817)^+$ is observed with statistical significance greater than 10σ . The mass and width of $a_0(1817)^+$ are measured to be $(1.817 \pm 0.008_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.020_{\text{syst.}})$ GeV/ c^2 and $(0.097 \pm 0.022_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.015_{\text{syst.}})$ GeV, respectively. However, the nature of $a_0(1817)^+$ is not set in stone. It seems that $a_0(1817)^+$ is the candidate of isovector partner of $f_0(1710)$ but the mass is about 100 MeV/ c^2 greater than what it supposed to be. The higher mass may imply $a_0(1817)^+$ is the isovector partner of the $X(1817)$ instead. Thus, the simultaneous amplitude analysis of $D_s^+ \rightarrow K_S^0 K^+ \pi^0$ and $D_s^+ \rightarrow K_S^0 K_S^0 \pi^+$ is crucial to solving this problem. Furthermore, the BF ratio of $a_0(980)^+ \rightarrow \bar{K}^0 K^+$ and $a_0(980)^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \eta$ is calculated to be $(13.7 \pm 3.6_{\text{stat.}} \pm 4.2_{\text{syst.}})\%$ which is a key important input for the calculation of the coupling constants of the $a_0(980)^+$ and helps determine its quark composition, and the BF ratio of $D_s^+ \rightarrow K^*(892)^0 K^+$ and $D_s^+ \rightarrow \bar{K}^0 K^*(892)^+$ is determined to be $2.35_{-0.23}^{+0.42}_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.10_{\text{syst.}}$.

Figure 1: Cited from Ref. [13]. The projections onto (a) $M_{K_S^0 K^+}$, (b) $M_{K_S^0 \pi^0}$, and (c) $M_{K^+ \pi^0}$. The data samples are represented by points with error bars, the fit results by blue lines, and backgrounds by black lines. Colored dashed lines show the components of the fit model.

3.2 Strong phase measurements

For final states including Cabibbo-favored (CF) and doubly Cabibbo-suppressed (DCS) process, like $K^- \pi^+$, $K^- \pi^+ \pi^0$ and $K^- \pi^+ \pi^+ \pi^-$, they have good sensitivity of γ/ϕ_3 in ADS method. Recently, BESIII has reported a study of $D \rightarrow K^- \pi^+$ by using a sample of QC $D\bar{D}$ pairs [14]. The asymmetry between CP -odd and CP -even eigenstate decays into $K^- \pi^+$ is determined to be $A_{K\pi} = 0.132 \pm 0.011_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.007_{\text{syst.}}$. Using the predominantly CP -even tag $D \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- \pi^0$ and the ensemble of CP -odd eigenstate tags, the observable $A_{K\pi}^{\pi\pi\pi^0}$ is measured to be $0.130 \pm 0.012_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.008_{\text{syst.}}$. These two asymmetries are sensitive to $r_D^{K\pi} \cos \delta_D^{K\pi}$, where $r_D^{K\pi}$ and $\delta_D^{K\pi}$ are the ratio of amplitudes and phase difference, respectively, between the DCS and CF decays. By studying events containing $D \rightarrow K^- \pi^+$ tagged by $D \rightarrow K_{S,L}^0 \pi^+ \pi^-$, $\delta_D^{K\pi}$ is measured to be $(187.6_{-9.7}^{+8.9+5.4})$ where external constraint is applied for $r_D^{K\pi}$. This is the most precise measurement of $\delta_D^{K\pi}$ in QC $D\bar{D}$ decays. In addition, the BF's of three K_L^0 modes are determined to be $\mathcal{B}(D^0 \rightarrow K_L^0 \pi^0) = (0.97 \pm 0.03_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.02_{\text{syst.}})\%$, $\mathcal{B}(D^0 \rightarrow K_L^0 \omega) = (1.09 \pm 0.06_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.03_{\text{syst.}})\%$ and $\mathcal{B}(D^0 \rightarrow K_L^0 \pi^0 \pi^0) = (1.26 \pm 0.05_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.03_{\text{syst.}})\%$.

4 Λ_c^+ decay studies with the threshold production

4.1 Overview

Λ_c^+ is the ground states of singly charmed baryon, and most of the charmed baryons and bottom baryons will eventually decay into Λ_c^+ final state. However, the knowledge of Λ_c^+ decays is still very limited in comparison with charmed mesons. The total exclusive decays of Λ_c^+ account for only about 60% of the total BF [15]. Λ_c^+ provides an excellent platform for understanding non-perturbative QCD and weak decay mechanism. In several phenomenological models, the Λ_c^+ hadronic decay amplitudes consist of factorizable and non-factorizable topological diagrams. The non-factorizable diagrams can not yet be calculated and need input from experimental measurements. Therefore, it is important to perform comprehensive and precise experimental measurements to validate different phenomenological models.

4.2 Semi-leptonic decays

4.2.1 $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda e^+ \nu_e$

The decay $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda e^+ \nu_e$ is the dominant decay channel of Λ_c^+ semi-leptonic decays, which is crucial for testing and calibrating theoretical calculations of differential decay rates and form factors. Recently, BESIII collaboration has reported an improved measurement of the absolute BF of $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda e^+ \nu_e$, $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda e^+ \nu_e) = (3.56 \pm 0.11 \pm 0.07)\%$ [16]. The precision of the world average is improved more than threefold. Combining $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda e^+ \nu_e)$ measured in this work, lifetime τ_{Λ_c} and the q^2 -integrated rate predicted by LQCD [17], we determined $|V_{cs}| =$

$0.936 \pm 0.017_{\mathcal{B}} \pm 0.024_{\text{LQCD}} \pm 0.0007_{\tau_{\Lambda_c}}$. Furthermore, by analyzing the dynamics of $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda e^+ \nu_e$, we measure the $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda$ decay form factors for the first time. The first direct comparisons on the differential decay rates and form factors with those obtained from LQCD calculations are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Cited from Ref. [16]. Comparisons of form factors (a) and the differential decay rates (b) with LQCD calculations. The band shows the total uncertainty.

4.2.2 $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow pK^- e^+ \nu_e$

A first study of the semi-leptonic decays $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow pK^- e^+ \nu_e$, $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda(1405)e^+ \nu_e$ and $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda(1520)e^+ \nu_e$ has been performed by BESIII collaboration [18]. The $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow pK^- e^+ \nu_e$ decay is observed with a significance of 8.2σ and the BF is measured to be $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow pK^- e^+ \nu_e) = (0.88 \pm 0.17_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.07_{\text{syst.}}) \times 10^{-3}$, which provides a clear confirmation that Λ_c^+ semi-leptonic decays are not saturated by $\Lambda l^+ \nu_l$. The evidences of $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda(1405)e^+ \nu_e$ and $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda(1520)e^+ \nu_e$ are reported with significances of 3.2σ and 3.3σ , respectively. The BFs are measured to be $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda(1405)[\rightarrow pK^-]e^+ \nu_e) = (0.42 \pm 0.19_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.04_{\text{syst.}}) \times 10^{-3}$ and $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda(1520)[\rightarrow pK^-]e^+ \nu_e) = (1.02 \pm 0.52_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.11_{\text{syst.}}) \times 10^{-3}$.

4.3 Hadronic decays

4.3.1 $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda\pi^+\pi^0$

BESIII collaboration has performed a partial wave analysis of the charmed baryon hadronic decay $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda\pi^+\pi^0$ for the first time [19]. The helicity amplitude fit procedure is implemented by TF-PWA [20]. Making use of the world-average BF $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda\pi^+\pi^0)$, the BFs of decaying into the intermediate states are determined to be $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda\rho(770)^+) = (4.06 \pm 0.30_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.35_{\text{syst.}} \pm 0.23_{\mathcal{B}}) \times 10^{-2}$, $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma(1385)^+\pi^0) = (5.86 \pm 0.49_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.52_{\text{syst.}} \pm 0.35_{\mathcal{B}}) \times 10^{-3}$ and $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma(1385)^0\pi^+) = (6.47 \pm 0.59_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.66_{\text{syst.}} \pm 0.38_{\mathcal{B}}) \times 10^{-3}$. In addition, the decay asymmetry parameters are measured to be $\alpha_{\Lambda\rho(770)^+} = -0.763 \pm 0.053_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.045_{\text{syst.}}$, $\alpha_{\Sigma(1385)^+\pi^0} = -0.917 \pm 0.069_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.056_{\text{syst.}}$ and $\alpha_{\Sigma(1385)^0\pi^+} = -0.789 \pm 0.098_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.056_{\text{syst.}}$. The non-factorizable topological diagrams contribute to the decays $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Lambda\rho(770)^+$ and $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma(1385)\pi$. This measurement provides a crucial input to improve and extend the current understanding of the dynamics of the charmed baryon hadronic decays.

4.3.2 $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma^0 K^+$ and $\Sigma^+ K_S^0$

Two singly Cabibbo-suppressed decays $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma^0 K^+$ and $\Sigma^+ K_S^0$ are studied by BESIII collaboration [21]. After taking the world-average branching fractions of the reference decay channels $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma^0 \pi^+$ and $\Sigma^+ \pi^+ \pi^-$, the BFs $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma^0 K^+)$ and $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma^+ K_S^0)$ are determined to be $(4.7 \pm 0.9_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.1_{\text{syst.}} \pm 0.3_{\text{ref.}}) \times 10^{-4}$ and $(4.8 \pm 1.4_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.2_{\text{syst.}} \pm 0.3_{\text{ref.}}) \times 10^{-4}$, respectively. The

BF of the $\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma^+ K_S^0$ decay is measured for the first time. The BF ratio of these two decays are calculated to be $\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma^0 K^+)/\mathcal{B}(\Lambda_c^+ \rightarrow \Sigma^+ K_S^0) = 0.98 \pm 0.35_{\text{stat.}} \pm 0.04_{\text{syst.}} \pm 0.08_{\text{ref.}}$.

5 Summary

BESIII has made great progress in the field of charm physics. More studies about the charm meson and baryon decays are proceeding and the results will be published very soon. In the future, BESIII plans to complete 20 fb^{-1} at center-of-mass energies of 3.773 GeV [1] and more results in hadronic charm meson decays can be expected. Furthermore, BEPCII plans to make upgrade of improving luminosity by 3 times higher than current BEPCII at 4.7 GeV, and the maximum energy will be extended to 5.6 GeV. After than, we will have opportunities to study other charmed baryons, such as Σ_c , Ξ_c and Ω_c in the BEPCII-U.

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